

ОСНОВНЫЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ ФОНЕТИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В ТУРЕЦКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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MAIN ELEMENTS OF THE PHONETIC SYSTEM IN TURKISH LANGUAGES

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Согласные (шум) – это звуки с нерегулярной частотой (частотой). Другими словами, согласные — это вневременные звуки, которые не встречаются в определенное время и последовательность. Хотя в звуках, издаваемых дышащими существами, существует периодичность, такая особенность не наблюдается в звуках, издаваемых физическими существами. На самом деле в шуме есть вторичные тона. Но между ними нет такой гармонии, как в звучании

ABSTRACT

When studying the vowel system, it is necessary to examine what physiological movements are. In the ancient times, sounds were used as a means of communication. I want to note that, writing is used by humans to express the sounds in language. This issue shows that any sound depends on certain movements of speech parts. In linguistics, the sound we hear and the sum of the actions that make it up are called phonemes. These are interrelated.

Ключевые слова: согласные звуки, гласные звуки, язык, турецкий язык, диалекты.

Keywords: consonant sounds, vowel sounds, language, Turkish, dialects.

Introduction. The structure of the sound system of Turkic languages, which has a very ancient history, has undergone many changes since ancient times. These changes experienced in those languages before reaching our modern times caused certain differences in the sound system of the language. These differences manifest themselves in both vowel sounds and consonant sounds.

Methods: Theoretical analysis and generalization; comparative qualitative; empirical methods: observation, interview.

Phonemes are abstract basic sounds, while allophones/variable sounds are concrete sounds that can change due to environmental factors. For example, the difference in meaning between the words "suLu/suCu" is due to the phonemes "L" and "C". Again, the phonemes "N" and "P" provide the difference in meaning in the words "saNik/perverted". But in the following examples, for example, we can see the changing sounds of the phoneme "N". We can observe that these variable sounds do not have a meaning-separating function. "manda: before d, kanbur: before g(e) of front palate, kanka: before k(a) of back palate, od: before g(i) of back palate, kanbur: before b".

The "n" sounds in the examples are sounds that are produced differently during speech under the influence of environmental factors. Whether the speaker uses these sounds incorrectly, knowingly or unknowingly, for example, if he uses the n sound before the frontal g in the word "fire", this can be a speech disorder.

Although it attracts the attention of the listener, the meaning of the word does not change for either the speaker or the listener. Therefore, the sound "n" in the examples given here are only allophones of the phoneme "N" (variable sounds) and are not related to the

meaning of the words, but to the pronunciation. In other words, "A phoneme can only be pronounced through the allophones within it. It is an abstract unity because it can never be spoken alone. Allophones are phonemes.

It is formed and pronounced as a result of the change of the pronunciation movement due to the influence of neighboring sounds; From this point of view, they are concrete associations." [1, p. 41]. According to Saussure, "a phoneme is not a sound, it can only be represented by a sound."

Phonemes appear in two parts: "segmental phonemes" and "segmental phonemes/combined phonemes". Segmented phonemes include vowel and consonant phonemes in the language. These phonemes are so named because they are in separate pieces. Regarding segmental phonemes in Turkish and many world languages; Vowels, consonants, and floating vowels (semivowels/semivowels) come to mind, showing both vowel and consonant characteristics. Suprasegmental phonemes are pronunciation features that involve more than one phoneme. The ones used in Turkish are: "speed", "wind pressure", "harmony", "tone change" and "melody" [2, p. 41]. Here we will focus more on the distinguishing features of "segmented phonemes".

Segmented phonemes are distinguished by their different characteristics. For example, we find the phonemes "p" and "b" in the words "pak" and "bak-". In fact, these two consonants are not only "bilabial consonants" but also "explosive" consonants due to the point of phoneme articulation. The contrast between these two phonemes, which have very similar properties, presents them as two separate phonemes. In other words, it is a "distinctive feature". The contrast or distinguishing feature between the phoneme "p" and the phoneme

"b" is whether or not the vocal cords vibrate during the formation of these phonemes. In this regard, the phoneme "b" differs from the phoneme "p", which does not vibrate the vocal cords, because it vibrates the vocal cords. This distinctive feature exists only for consonant phonemes. Because all vowels come into contact with the vocal cords during formation and vibrate the vocal cords. However, although some of the consonants come into contact with the vocal cords when they are produced (toned/voiced/soft/voiced consonants: b, c, d, g, ğ...), some vibrate the vocal cords. when the vocal cords are formed from them (toneless/silent/hard/unvoiced: p, ç, t, k, s, sh...) they do not come into contact with the vocal cords and do not cause vibration in the vocal cords. Here, vibrativity and non-vibration contrast such as p:b, ç:c, t:d... is one of the aspects that distinguish phonemes (kam-gam, pulbul-, tik-dik-, at-ad, is-iz). ...). This distinctive feature refers to the tonal counterpart, "reciprocal consonants". Since the points of articulation of mutual consonants are the same, they have such a different meaning. Non-reciprocal consonant phonemes (consonants m, n, l, r, and y without toneless equivalents and consonant h without tone equivalent) do not perform a meaning discriminating function, as there is no similar contrast.

There is a point of articulation where all vowel and consonant sounds are formed. The variability of this point of inflection is one of the distinguishing features of phonemes. For example, the phonemes that distinguish meaning in the cancellation words "biz, boz, bez, buz, buz-, baz" are the vowel phonemes "i-o-eu-ü-a". The distinguishing features of these vowel phonemes are mainly the change of the places of articulation during articulation and, accordingly, the shape of some speech organs (such as the opening of the mouth, the shape of the lips). Vowels and consonants should be evaluated separately according to their places of articulation.

Vowels are sounds produced in the oral cavity. The main organ in the production of these sounds is the tongue, which moves freely in the mouth. Vowel sounds are mainly produced in the tongue and are classified as front vowels (i, e, ü, ö), middle vowels (i) and back vowels (a, u, o), respectively. As the articulation of vowels changes, so does the meaning of the word. "bald/cal-, bush/ash, you/you-, treble/salt..."

We can mention the distinguishing features of consonants according to the place of articulation as follows - various classifications and detailed information will be given in the following sections:

Lipized consonants: "b, p, m".

Dental labial consonants "f, v".

Dental consonants: "d, t, n, s, z, l, r".

Consonants after the teeth: "c, ç, j, ş".

Front, middle palatal consonants: "k (k of the front and back palate), g (g of the front and back palate), y".

Laryngeal consonant: "h".

Vowel and consonant phonemes also have distinctive features according to the form of expression, in other words, voice and respiratory tract.

Vowel phonemes, depending on the form of pronunciation, have two distinguishing features in terms of mouth opening and lip shape when pronouncing vowels:

In this regard, vowels can be divided into 3 parts: narrow vowels (i, ü, u, ı), middle vowels (e, ö, o) and wide vowels (a). [3, p. 41]. "The term "narrow" here means "wide enough not to cause friction" distance" means. The terms ", "medium" and "wide" mean "openness that is easily accessible and does not reach the point of difficulty". [4, p. 93]. Therefore, when phonemes. in terms of opening the mouth, it is replaced by different articulations, the meanings of the words also change. "girl/kaz, all/tam, peş/pish-, kul/kol/kal-/kel/ash/kil/kil" Actually, since the points of articulation of the phonemes classified with the same feature are not exactly the same. they also have specific characteristics and meanings. It is used as discrimination. For example, the vowels "e, o, ö", which we call middle consonants, are arranged backwards from the middle of the tongue like "e, ö, o". For this reason, each of these is an independent phoneme that differentiates the meaning: "come-/goal/lake, bald/bush, check-/collapse-/cook".

References

1. Omer Demircan (1978), p. 41.
2. Omer Demircan (1978), p. 41.
3. Omer Demircan (1978), p. 41.
4. Ozcan Başkan (2003), p. 93.